

A simulation of cycling activists affecting change in behavior

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Problem

An important question has plagued urban developers, policymakers, environmental researchers for decades: do activists and promoters of cycling affect change in behaviour with urban dwellers and their exposure to particulate matter (PM)? While this might not be in the forefront of the scientific community, we set out to explore this question in a virtual environment. A simulation with a stochastic model, e.g., agent-based model (ABM), is a simpler and cheaper option. Individuals and their behaviour are simulated in a virtual environment, based only on population and aggregated research data. The authors acknowledge that this is not a substitute for real-world research. Rather, it is an exploration to provide another tool to design better research.

Solution

An ABM was constructed in Netlogo (Figure 1), assessing exposure of 100 individuals to PM. Their actions were governed by inherent probabilities of performing an activity, based on population data, e.g., a ~33% probability of sleeping. Each activity was associated with (1) an intensity level, determining how vigorous an activity is, and how it affects their minute ventilation (amount of air they breathe in one minute), and (2) a pollution level of PM, based on published research. A certain percentage of agents were so called activists, individual agents that prompt other agents to reduce their probability of choosing a car/bus as their mode of transport, rather opting for walking/cycling. Each hour agents select an activity based on the modified probabilities.

Results show that simply increasing the share of activists or their influence does not increase the intake dose of PM, if the concentration of PM is relatively low. When the outdoor concentration of PM increases, the activists play an ever-increasing role in elevating the intake dose of individuals.

These models can be further augmented, enhanced and calibrated based on outcomes of real-world exposure research.

Figure 1: Visualization of the Graphic user interface of the ABM